

ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF CILNIDIPINE AND METOPROLOL SUCCINATE IN BULK AND TABLET FORMULATION BY RP-HPLC METHOD

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Abstract:

The present work involves a new method was established that is development and validation of RP-HPLC method for the estimation of cilnidipine and metoprolol succinate in their combination dosage form. In this HPLC method X-Terra C18 column (250 X4.6 mm ID) was used as SP and phosphate buffer, Acetonitrile in the ratio of 40: 60 as a MP was used. The flow rate was 1.2ml/min. & isobestic point of both drugs were quantified at 254 nm. The retention time for cilnidipine and metoprolol succinate was found to be 2.5mins and 10.5 mins respectively. The analytical method was validated according to ICH guidelines²¹ (ICH, Q2 (R1)). The linearity for Cilnidipine and Metoprolol Succinate was found in concentration range of 1-10 μ g/ml & 5-100 μ g/ml and Correlation coefficient (R^2) value for both drugs was found to be 0.999, % recovery was found to be 99.6 to 100.00. RSD for method precision was 0.21 & 0.11. Hence the suggested RP-HPLC method can be used for routine analysis of Cilnidipine and Metoprolol Succinate in API and Pharmaceutical dosage form.

Key words: cilnidipine and metoprolol succinate, method development, validation, HPLC.

Introduction

Cilnidipine is the calcium channel blocker. It blocks the L-type calcium channels in blood vessels and the N-type calcium channels in sympathetic nerve endings. It also dilates arterioles & used in treatment of hypertension. Chemically it is noted as 1, 4-Dihydro-2, 6-dimethyl-4-(3-nitrophenyl)-3, 5- pyridine Carboxylic acid-2-methoxy ethyl (2E)-3-phenyl-propenyl ester. Metoprolol succinate (MET) is a cardio selective drug used alone or combination with other medicines to treat hypertension and various cardiovascular disorders. The action of Metoprolol succinate is mediated through the β_1 -selective adreno receptor blockage, thus causing reduction in heart rate and cardiac output. Its chemical name is described as (\pm) 1- (isopropyl amino)-3-[p-(2 methoxy ethyl) phenoxy]-2-propanol succinate (2:1)

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chemical structure of Cilnidipine and Metoprolol succinate were shown
figure 1.

Fig: 1- Chemical structure of Cilnidipine and Metoprolol Succinate

Based on various referred journals literature we quantify the selected combination drugs in its category. So, an attempt has been made to develop an accurate, precise and economically reliable RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of combination the current research. In this the method was developed and explained by validation parameters according to ICH guidelines.

Materials and Methods:**Chemical and standers used:**

Pharmaceutical grade Cilnidipine and metoprolol succinate pure samples were purchased from prudence pharma chem. & par drugs, Mumbai respectively. Metoprolol succinate and cilnidipine tablets were purchased from local market, Orthophosphoric acid, Potassium di hydrogen ortho phosphate, Di potassium hydrogen ortho phosphate & Methanol from Merck, Acetonitrile obtained from Fischer scientific.

Instruments used:

HPLC-auto sampler-UV detector model number ACME 9000, Electronic balance, Sonicator, Vacuum pump. These instruments are used for the estimation of cilnidipine and metoprolol succinate.

Chromatographic Condition:

C18 column, 250mm × 4.6 mm, 5µm was used for the chromatographic separation at a detection wave length of 254 nm. Mobile phase of composition phosphate buffer: Acetonitrile (40:60) was selected for elution and same mixture was used in the preparation of standard and sample solutions. Flow rate was adjusted to 1.2 ml/min.

Preparation of 0.02M Phosphate buffer:

Buffer was prepared by dissolving 2.72g of Potassium di hydrogen orthophosphate (KH₂PO₄) and 5.45 gm of K₂HPO₄ in 1L of water and followed by the degassing of the solution.

Preparation of mobile phase:

Phosphate buffer and acetonitrile were filtered separately through 0.45µ membrane filters. The filtered solvents were mixed in the ratio of 40:60 and degassed by sonicator for 10mins. The resulting solutions is used as a mobile phase.

Diluent Preparation:

1L of diluent was prepared by mixing 400 ml of 0.02 M Phosphate Buffer and 600 ml of Acetonitrile in the ratio of (40:60).

Preparation of stock solution:

Accurately weighed 10 mg of the both Cilnidipine and Metoprolol Succinate was transferred to 10 ml clean and dry volumetric flask. Then the volume was made up to the mark with the diluent and mixed well. This yielded a stock solution with concentration 1000 ppm of Cilnidipine and Metoprolol Succinate mixture.

Preparation of standard solution:

A Quantity of 0.1 and 0.5 ml of the Cilnidipine with Metoprolol Succinate stock was transferred to 10 ml clean and dried out volumetric flask, make up the volume with diluent this yielded a standard stock solution and concentrations of 10 ppm and 50 ppm of Cilnidipine and Metoprolol Succinate respectively.

Preparation of sample solution:

Take 20 tablets and weighed, determined the average weight and crushed to fine powder. weighed accurately tablet powder equivalent to 10 mg of both were transferred into 10 ml volumetric flask, 3 ml of diluents added and sonicated for 30 min in cold water. Finally the volume was made using diluents and filtered.

Procedure: 20 µl of the filtered portion of sample and standard preparations were injected into the HPLC System. The responses for the major peaks were recorded and the content of cilnidipine and metoprolol succinate in each tablet were calculated.

Validation parameters:**1. Specificity**

The system suitability for specificity was carried out to determine whether there are any interference of any impurities in retention time of analytical peak. The study was performed by injecting blank.

The specificity test was performed for cilnidipine and metoprolol succinate. It was found that there was no interference of impurities in retention time of analytical peak (Table: 1).

S.No.	Name	RT[min]	Area[µV*s]	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor	Resolution
1	Cilnidipine	2.6000	1693185	4416.5	1.2727	0.0000
2	Metoprolol Succinate	10.966	10683542	13650.6	1.1667	16.0097
Avg.			12376727			

Table 1:-Specificity values of cilnidipine & metoprolol succinate

Fig-2: Chromatogram showing blank succinate

Fig-3: std. chromatogram for cilnidipine and metoprolol

2. Linearity:

Preparation of standard stock solution:

Accurately weighed 10 mg of the both Cilnidipine and MET was transferred in to 10 ml fresh and dry volumetric flask, dissolve by adding the solvent. After that the solution was made up to the mark with the diluent and mix well. This yield a stock solution was 1000 ppm of Cilnidipine with MET mixture. A linear relationship was evaluated across the range of the analytical procedure. A series of standard dilutions were prepared from the working standard solution in the concentration range of 1-20 µg/ml of cilnidipine and 5-100 µg/ml of MET respectively. 10 µl of each solution was injected into HPLC system. Linearity is evaluated by plotting the peak area as a function of analyte concentrations.

Cilnidipine Conc. (ppm)	Area	Metoprolol Succinate Conc. (ppm)	Area
1	162977	5.00	1191522
2	379529	10.00	2625242
5	886552	25.00	5980483
10	1733185	50.00	12683542
15	2680862	75.00	17962262
20	3617684	100.00	24286576

Table 2: Linearity values for Cilnidipine and Metoprolol Succinate

Fig-4: Linearity Curve of Cilnidipine

Fig-5: Linearity Curve of Metoprolol Succinate

3. Accuracy:

Method procedure: Prepared solutions in triplicate at levels 50%, 100% and 150% of test concentrations using for Cilnidipine and Metoprolol Succinate working Standards as per the test method and injected each solution in triplicate.

Table

Cilnidipine				
Conc.		inj-1	inj-2	inj-3
5pm	50%	835725	833847	841376
10ppm	100%	1682715	1695625	1688714
15pm	150%	2598925	2528186	2527814
Mean		836982.7	1689018	2551642
% Recovery		98.72261	99.61035	100.3226
STD		3918.897	6460.367	40948.99
% RSD		0.468217	0.382492	1.60481
Metoprolol Succinate				
25ppm	50%	6218243	6252453	6238632
50ppm	100%	12689542	12678013	12686825
75ppm	150%	19256724	19186535	19256243
Mean		6236443	12684793	19233167
% Recovery		98.33913	100.0099	101.0925
STD		17209.76	6027.04	40385.5
% RSD		0.275955	0.047514	0.209978

3:

Accuracy results for Cilnidipine and Metoprolol succinate

The recovery results showing that the test method was acceptable level of accuracy for the assay of Cilnidipine and Metoprolol Succinate was from 80% to 120% of test concentration (Table 3).

4. Precision

Six individual preparations were prepared using single batch of Cilnidipine and Metoprolol Succinate working standard as per test method and injected each solutions.

	Injection-1	Injection-2	Average	MEAN	SD	% RSD
Cilnidipine						
MP-1	1693185	1695625	1694405	1695625.7	3713.4677	0.2190028
MP-2	1694827	1697643	1696235			
MP-3	1689004	1688643	1688823.5			
MP-4	1697265	1699972	1698618.5			
MP-5	1699264	1697624	1698444			
MP-6	1695732	1698724	1697228			
Metoprolol succinate						
MP-1	12683542	12679277	12681409.5	12676515	14700.88	0.11596941
MP-2	12677634	12673827	12675730.5			
MP-3	12693827	12685428	12689627.5			
MP-4	12664826	12673872	12669349			
MP-5	12642922	12664826	12653874			
MP-6	12699277	12678922	12689099.5			

Table 4: Precision values for Cilnidipine and Metoprolol succinate

Results The %RSD value found to be less than 2 and hence the result found to be satisfactory (Table 4).

5. Ruggedness:

Method Procedure: The standard solution was individually prepared as per the test method and injected each solution in six times using different system, analyst, and date.

Method/Procedure: samples were prepared as per the test method the test method and injected in duplicate using different system, analyst on different day. Calculated Mean area, SD, %RSD.¹⁸

Acceptance Criteria: Overall RSD should not be more than 2.0 %.

Based on the results of % RSD as per Table-4: The %RSD value found to be less than 2 and hence the result found to be satisfactory (Table 4).

6. Limit of detection

Lowest amount of analyte in a sample that can be detected but not necessarily quantities, under the stated experimental conditions.

Fig-6: Chromatogram showing LOD: (0.015 & 0.075ppm)

The LOD was performed for cilnidipine and metoprolol succinate was found to be 2.97 and 2.93 (Table 5).

7. Limit of quantification:

S.NO	Drug name(conc)	S	N	LOQ (S/N)
1	Cilnidipine (0.05)	457	46	9.93
2	Metoprolol Succinate(0.25)	459	46	9.97

Table 6: Signal-to- Noise Ratio

for LOQ

Fig-7: Chromatogram showing LOQ: (0.05 & 0.25ppm)

The LOQ was performed for cilnidipine and metoprolol succinate was found to be 9.93 and 9.97 (Table 6).

8. Robustness:

Preparation of standard solution:

Accurately weighed amount of 0.1 and 0.5 ml of the Cilnidipine and Metoprolol Succinate Stock Solution transferred to 10 ml clean and dried volumetric flask. After that make up the quantity up to the mark with diluent and well mixed. Finally, the standard stock solution with Concentrations of 10 ppm and 50 ppm of Cilnidipine and Metoprolol Succinate respectively.

Method procedure:

1. Flow: The standard solution was prepared and injected for the two times with (± 1) flowrate.

2. Mobile Phase: The standard solution was prepared and injected for the two times with (± 5)

Mobile Phase composition. Appraise of its capability to remain unchanged by minute, but Conscious variations in process parameters and provides signal of its reliability during its normal usage.

Procedure: samples were analysed under the following conditions

Cilnidipine ±					
Parameters	Adjusted TO	Avg. Area ^a	T	SD	% RSD
Flow Rate	1.1 ml/min	1941793.3	3.81	27659.22	1.42
	As per method	1697450.5	2.63	1838.27	0.11
1.2ml/min	1.3 ml/min	1342340.33	2.24	13818.70	1.21
	35:65	1854049.83	2.36	20210.20	1.09
Mobile phase comp ⁿ (40:60v/v, Buffer: Acetonitrile)	As it is	1697450.5	2.63	1838.27	0.11
	45:55	1496583.33	3.94	3097.23	0.24
Metoprolol Succinate					
Flow Rate As per method	1.1 ml/min	18270502	13.64	12826.87	0.07
	As it is	12676652	10.96	11495.59	0.09
1.2ml/min	1.3 ml/min	6288153.00	7.42	7390.12	0.12
	35:65	16047539	8.66	15528.59	0.10
Mobile phase comp ⁿ (40:60v/v, Buffer: Acetonitrile)	As it is	12676652	10.96	11495.59	0.09
	45:55	8477340.2	12.15	8126.60	0.10

Table 7: Robustness values for Cilnidipine and Metoprolol succinate

Fig-8: Chromatogram showing more flow rate

Fig-9: Chromatogram showing less flow rate

9. System suitability

Preparation of standard solution:

Accurately amount of 0.1 and 0.5 ml of the Cilnidipine and Metoprolol Succinate stock solution transferred to 10 ml clean and dried volumetric flask. Subsequently make up the amount up to the mark with diluent and well mixed.

Finally the standard stock solution with concentrations of 10 ppm and 50 ppm of Cilnidipine and Metoprolol Succinate respectively.

Procedure: Standard solution was prepared and injected six times to test the performance of the chromatographic instrument.

Conc. of Clini. & Metop.	Injection	Area of Cilnidipine	RT(min)	Area of Metoprolol	RT(min)
10 & 50ppm	Inj-1	1695732	2.62	12697634	10.95
	Inj-2	1697265	2.64	12675428	10.96
	Inj-3	1698972	2.62	12676922	10.93
	Inj-4	1694827	2.65	12669277	10.97
	Inj-5	1698643	2.63	12676827	10.94
	Inj-6	1699264	2.63	12663826	10.98
Statistical Analysis	Mean	1697450.5	2.631667	12676652.33	10.955
	SD	1838.271226	0.01169	11495.58981	0.018708
	% RSD	0.108296014	0.444222	0.090683167	0.170774
	Tailing Factor (TF)	1.27		1.16	
	Plate Count (PC)	4416.5		13650.6	

Table 8: System Suitability values for Cilnidipine and Metoprolol succinate

Conclusion

The developed RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of Cilnidipine and Metoprolol Succinate is a precise, accurate, and reliable analytical technique. The method demonstrated good resolution between the two drugs, with appropriate selectivity, sensitivity, and reproducibility. The calibration curves for both Cilnidipine and Metoprolol Succinate exhibited excellent linearity, making the method suitable for routine quality control analysis in pharmaceutical formulations. The results confirm that the method can be effectively applied for the quantification of these drugs in bulk and in tablet formulations, ensuring compliance with regulatory standards. The developed method offers a fast, efficient, and cost-effective solution for the simultaneous estimation of Cilnidipine and Metoprolol Succinate in pharmaceutical products.

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